

LAW AND ORDER: A NEURO-SYMBOLIC SYSTEM FOR TAX LAW AUTOFORMALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Legal systems are increasingly implemented through software, yet scalable methods for translating legal texts into accurate symbolic representations remain underdeveloped. We study this problem through tax law, where forms and filing instructions define large computational structures composed of arithmetic, branching, recursion, and tabular reasoning. We introduce a neuro-symbolic framework for the automatic formalization of tax forms and tax-form instructions into executable symbolic programs. Our approach is based on two forms of correspondence between law and logic: structural correspondence, which aligns legal and symbolic components such as cells and schedules, and denotational correspondence, which requires each symbolic component to preserve the meaning of its legal counterpart. We combine large language model synthesis with cell-level verification and an agentic repair loop that iteratively localizes and corrects errors using benchmark tax returns. Evaluated on 30 tax forms from TaxCalcBench and OpenTaxSolver, the framework achieves 100% agreement with benchmark outputs at the cell level. Rather than measuring a single generation pass, this result reflects the performance of the complete neuro-symbolic formalization system. Our work provides both a practical approach to large-scale legal auto-formalization and a foundation for evaluating correspondence between legal texts and executable symbolic representations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern societies are increasingly governed through formalized representations of law (de la Garza, 2020; Lessig, 2009). Tax systems, regulatory compliance frameworks, and safety-critical decision systems all depend on symbolic representations that operationalize legal rules originally written in natural language. Yet despite growing interest in legal formalization, the automated pipeline from legal text to verified symbolic logic remains an open problem. Existing auto-formalization methods are still heavily concentrated in mathematics (Jiang et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2026). In expert legal domains, formalization remains largely manual, expensive, and difficult to scale (Lawsky, 2026; Holzenberger et al., 2020). For example, Direct File required 16 million U.S. dollars and more than two years to build (Treasury Inspector General for Tax Administration, 2026). Beyond niche applications to small legal text snippets (Judson et al., 2024; Lawsky, 2022), scalable automated legal formalization has yet to be realized.

Tax law provides a particularly challenging but important setting for legal formalization. The difficulty lies not only in the complexity of legal interpretation, but also in the size and structure of the artifacts to be formalized. Existing tax-form implementations, such as OpenTaxSolver (Roberts, 2026), contain more than 70k lines of code, and individual forms such as Form 1040 can exceed 1k lines of code. Moreover, not every source of tax law can be translated directly into software without substantial interpretation. As shown in Figure 1, higher-level legal sources, such as constitutional provisions and statutes, are refined into increasingly operational materials, including regulations, guidance, forms, and eventually software.

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Figure 1: Law composes through refinement.

Our system focuses on IRS tax forms and tax form instructions. These documents are designed for American English speakers, rather than exclusively for legal experts, and are therefore more concrete and operational than statutes or the Code of Federal Regulations.

Language-wise: Tax form instructions are not drafted primarily for lawyers, but for ordinary taxpayers in the United States. As a result, they are generally less ambiguous than statutes and regulations and require substantially less legal interpretation. The interpretive knowledge needed to read them is largely within the competence expected of ordinary tax filers, half of whom read at OECD/PIAAC Level 2, roughly corresponding to 6th- to 8th-grade literacy (Mamedova & Pawlowski, 2019).

Logic-wise: Tax form instructions are also more systematically organized. Statutes and regulations are often fragmented by amendments, cross-references, and dispersed provisions. By contrast, revisions to tax form instructions are typically consolidated and summarized at the beginning of each annual instruction document, leading to a more concise and coherent logical structure.

Law-wise: Although tax form instructions formally carry less legal authority than statutes or regulations, they exert substantial practical influence on taxpayer behavior. Forms and instructions are the primary interface through which most taxpayers experience the law, and they guide the actual process of compliance.

Each tax form consists of cells to be filled with numeric, Boolean, or finite-sort values. Some cells are inputs, requiring users to provide facts about themselves and their families. Other cells are computed from previous cells according to the filing instructions. These instructions specify how each value should be calculated using earlier values in the form. Thus, the formalization problem can be viewed as the task of translating a large body of natural-language instructions into executable logic involving arithmetic computation, branching, restricted recursion over previous cells, and operations over tabular data. Although each individual step is often simple, the scale of the form and the dependencies among cells make synthesis and validation difficult. In synthesis, errors can compound across cells, making localization essential. In validation, the feedback signal must be fine-grained enough to detect individual cell-level errors within the much larger structure of the form.

This setting requires symbolic representations that are structurally aligned with the legal texts they formalize. The representation must contain cell-level units corresponding to the cells of the tax form, and its submodules should align with the schedules, sections, and dependency structure of the original form. Once this structural correspondence is established, we can evaluate the denotational and functional equivalence between decomposed natural-language instructions and decomposed symbolic representations.

We therefore define when legal texts and executable symbolic representations are comparable and propose a framework for determining when the latter can be said to represent the former. This framework supports the analysis, validation, and comparison of legal formalizations independently of any particular implementation language or software system. By making the criteria for correspondence explicit, we aim to provide a foundation for rigorous evaluation of automated governance systems.

We present a neuro-symbolic system for tax law auto-formalization. The system combines three components: a synthesis module that translates tax forms and instructions into executable symbolic representations; a verification module that checks generated programs against benchmark returns

Algorithm 1: Generation, Verification and Correction of Tax-Form Symbolic Logic

Input: Test cases with cell-by-cell output $T = \{(I^{(1)}, G^{(1)}), \dots, (I^{(n)}, G^{(n)})\}$;
cell functions $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_m\}$;
instructions $\mathcal{I} = \{\mathcal{I}_1, \dots, \mathcal{I}_m\}$;
dependency structure over F
Output: Corrected cell functions F

repeat

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  // Execute computation graph on all test cases
  for  $(I^{(k)}, G^{(k)}) \in T$  do
    for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $m$  do
       $x_j^{(k)} \leftarrow$  inputs required by  $f_j$ ;
       $o_j^{(k)} \leftarrow f_j(x_j^{(k)})$ ;
    // Repair functions that disagree with NL reasoning
    for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $m$  do
      for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
        if  $o_j^{(k)} \neq G_j^{(k)}$  then
           $f_j \leftarrow$  LLMCorrect( $f_j, \{x_j^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^n, \mathcal{I}_j$ );
  until  $\forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, m\}, o_j^{(k)} = g_j^{(k)}$ ;
return  $F$ 

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and cell-level expected outputs; and an iterative repair loop that localizes discrepancies and revises the corresponding symbolic functions. In this way, the system performs test-driven legal formalization: it repeatedly generates, executes, verifies, and repairs the formalization until the generated program is consistent with the benchmark outputs.

General-purpose software testing is often insufficient for legal applications, where bugs are not merely system failures but potential misinterpretations of legal logic. Tax calculation is a high-stakes domain in which even small implementation errors can produce systematic failures. Our approach addresses this challenge by combining automated formalization with a specialized testing layer that evaluates whether the generated symbolic representation conforms to the intended legal and mathematical behavior of the form.

After the synthesis–verification loop converges, every evaluated cell matched the benchmark outputs for all tested forms and benchmark returns, yielding 100% cell accuracy and form accuracy on 30 forms across jurisdictions in TaxCalcBench (Bock et al., 2025) and OpenTaxSolver (?). This result should not be interpreted as the accuracy of a single LLM generation pass. Rather, it reflects the performance of the complete synthesis–verification system, which combines program generation, symbolic execution, discrepancy localization, and iterative correction until consistency is achieved.

By integrating rigorous cell-by-cell validation into the development loop, tax software operators, including government revenue agencies and accounting firms, can scale legal automation while maintaining the transparency and accountability required in high-stakes legal domains. More broadly, these techniques help ensure that, as legal services are increasingly automated, they preserve the due process, interpretability, and accuracy that citizens deserve.

2 METHOD

Our approach transforms tax forms in English and Spanish and their accompanying instructions into an executable symbolic representation assisted by easily available examples from the IRS website. The pipeline consists of three stages: (1) form structure extraction, (2) function signature generation, (3) instruction-grounded program synthesis and 4) test case-assisted verification and correction.

The objective of our system is to synthesize a symbolic program that exactly reproduces the computations specified by a tax form and its accompanying instructions. Let (P) denote the synthesized

program and let $(T = t_1, \dots, t_n)$ denote a collection of benchmark tax returns from the Open Tax Solver (OTS) test cases (Roberts, 2026). Each test case t_j contains a complete set of input values and expected outputs. We evaluate the synthesized functions by executing (F) on the test case inputs I_j and comparing the resulting cell values against the test case outputs G_j . We then employ an iterative synthesis–verification loop for symbolic logic generation.

2.1 FORM STRUCTURE EXTRACTION

Given a tax form, we first use a regex-based algorithm for extracting all computationally relevant cells and their associated definitions from the PDF file. Each cell and its definition corresponds to a function in the resulting symbolic representation.

To evaluate the reliability of this stage, we manually audited the extracted representations across a diverse collection of federal and state tax forms, including U.S. Form 1040 and its schedules, as well as tax forms from Arizona, California, Massachusetts, Michigan, New Jersey, New York, North Carolina, Ohio, Oregon, Pennsylvania, and Virginia. Across all audited forms, the extracted cell structures matched the source documents without observed errors.

2.2 FUNCTION SIGNATURE GENERATION

For each extracted cell, we generate an empty function specification that represents the computation required to determine the value of that cell. At this stage, only the function interface is generated; the implementation logic is intentionally omitted.

Formally, each cell $(c_i : \mathbb{N}|\mathbb{R}|\{\text{true}, \text{false}\})$ is associated with a function

$$f_i : X_i \rightarrow c_i \tag{1}$$

where (X_i) denotes the set of input variables referenced by the tax form. The resulting collection of function signatures defines the computational skeleton of the tax form while remaining agnostic to the underlying implementation language. The representation can be instantiated in any formal language capable of expressing executable symbolic logic, including Epilogue, C++, Lean, Python, or domain-specific languages.

As with the extraction stage, we manually verified the correctness of generated function signatures across all audited tax forms and observed no errors.

2.3 INSTRUCTION-GROUNDED PROGRAM SYNTHESIS

Tax forms are accompanied by official instructions that specify how each cell should be computed ¹. We leverage these instructions as the authoritative semantic source for program generation as they are specifically drafted for ordinary tax-payers, logically well-structured, and require substantially less legal interpretation than statutes and Code of Federal Regulations.

During this step, an LLM receives (1) the tax form, (2) the corresponding instruction text, and (3) the function signatures. The model synthesizes executable symbolic logic for each function signature that implements the computation described in the instructions. Conceptually, this stage performs a translation from natural-language legal rules into formal executable specifications. The synthesized logic may be expressed in any target formal language, provided that its expressivity allows for preservation of the semantics of the underlying tax instructions and can be executed deterministically.

2.4 TEST CASE-ASSISTED VERIFICATION AND CORRECTION

To validate the synthesized program, we compare its outputs—specifically, the cell values computed by each generated function—against independently generated test cases obtained from IRS forms. Each test case consists of a set of input variables together with the expected values for all cells in the form. Validation proceeds sequentially, comparing cell values step by step. When a discrepancy is

¹<https://www.irs.gov/pub/irs-pdf/i1040gi.pdf>

identified, the function corresponding to the affected cell is regenerated by prompting the LLM with the relevant tax form and instruction context to correct the implementation. The validation process is then repeated. This iterative refinement cycle continues until the outputs produced through symbolic execution match the independently generated test cases for every cell in the form.

Because tax forms define a deterministic computation graph, agreement at every intermediate cell implies agreement on the final tax outputs. Consequently, the final synthesized program is accepted only when it reproduces the complete computation trace without any inconsistencies.

2.5 ACCURACY MEASUREMENT

2.5.1 ACCURACY METRIC

We define cell-level accuracy as

$$\text{Cell Accuracy} = \frac{\# \text{ correctly computed cells}}{\# \text{ total evaluated cells}}. \quad (2)$$

A cell is considered correct if its value matches the output value for the corresponding test case.

A synthesized form is considered correct if all cells match the benchmark outputs across all evaluation cases. Form-level accuracy is therefore defined as:

$$\text{Form Accuracy} = \frac{\#\{\text{forms with zero incorrect cells}\}}{\#\{\text{total forms}\}}. \quad (3)$$

After the synthesis–verification loop converges, every evaluated cell matched the benchmark outputs for all tested forms and benchmark returns, yielding 100% cell-level accuracy and 100% form-level accuracy on the evaluation set.

Importantly, this result should not be interpreted as the accuracy of a single LLM generation pass. Rather, it reflects the accuracy of the complete synthesis–verification system, which combines program generation, symbolic execution, discrepancy localization, and iterative correction until consistency is achieved.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Model. We use GPT-5.5 xHigh as the LLM for symbolic logic translation and correction.

Testing data. For testing the performance of our system on federal tax returns, we use all the 51 test cases in TaxCalcBench. Each test case contains a set of user inputs and the corresponding expected tax-return output, along with a testing harness that checks whether a model’s output matches the correct result. For testing the performance of our system on state-level tax returns, we use test cases generated from the OpenTaxSolver.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We show the performance of our method in Figure 2. Performance clusters by model family, with GPT-5.4 variants forming the strongest neural baseline, followed by Claude Opus and Gemini Pro models, while smaller and efficiency-oriented variants exhibit substantially lower accuracy. The relatively narrow gap between the strongest and weakest frontier models compared to the gap between all LLMs and the neuro-symbolic system suggests that scaling alone is insufficient to solve this task. In contrast, the neuro-symbolic approach achieves 100% accuracy, reflecting the benefits of combining natural-language understanding with explicit symbolic representations and verifiable computation. By grounding reasoning in executable symbolic structures rather than purely statistical generation, the neuro-symbolic framework eliminates logical inconsistencies and ensures exact correspondence between the formalized procedure and the intended outcome. The neuro-symbolic

Figure 2: Performance of our neuro-symbolic method and large language models. The large language model results are taken from Tax-Calc-Bench (Bock et al., 2025). These include models from OpenAI: GPT-5.4 Pro, GPT-5.4, GPT-5 with Web Search, GPT-5.2 Pro, GPT-5.2, GPT-5; models from Anthropic: Claude Opus 4.6, Claude Sonnet 4.6, Claude Opus 4.5, Claude Sonnet 4.5, Claude Opus 4.1, Claude Opus 4, Claude Sonnet 4, Claude Haiku 4.5 with Web Search, Claude Haiku 4.5 and models from Google: Gemini 3.1 Pro, Gemini 3 Pro, Gemini 2.5 Pro, Gemini 2.5 Flash.

Figure 3: Distribution of calculation chain lengths for correct and incorrect GPT-5.5 predictions.

framework constrains reasoning through explicit, executable representations that are transparent, verifiable, and guaranteed to produce logically consistent outcomes. These results suggest that symbolic structure remains essential for domains such as taxation and law, where correctness is determined by adherence to formal rules rather than linguistic plausibility.

4 ANALYSIS

4.1 ACCURACY VS NUMBER OF ITERATIONS

From Figure 3, we show that errors are concentrated among examples with longer calculation chains, indicating that model accuracy decreases as reasoning depth increases. This pattern is consistent with the hypothesis that intermediate mistakes accumulate over multi-step computations, leading to a higher probability of failure on long reasoning trajectories. Similar phenomena have been reported in prior deductive reasoning and math reasoning benchmarks (Han et al., 2024; Miner et al., 2025) where model performance degrades as the length and complexity of the reasoning chain increase.

4.2 EXAMPLE

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/-- 2025 SALT cap (post-OBBA): base cap $40,000 ($20,000 MFS), reduced by 30% of
MAGI (~AGI) over $500,000 ($250,000 MFS), but not below the $10,000 ($5,000 MFS) floor. -/
def cell_072_a5e_limited_state_local_taxes (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  let baseCap := if i.isMarriedSeparate then 20000.0 else 40000.0
  let threshold := if i.isMarriedSeparate then 250000.0 else 500000.0
  let floorCap := if i.isMarriedSeparate then 5000.0 else 10000.0
  let reduced := baseCap - 0.30 * notLessThanZero (i.agi - threshold)
  let cap := if reduced < floorCap then floorCap else reduced
  smallerOf (cell_071_a5d_state_local_taxes i) cap

def cell_073_a7_total_taxes (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  cell_072_a5e_limited_state_local_taxes i + inputNum "A6" i

def cell_074_a8e_home_mortgage_interest (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  inputNum "A8a" i + inputNum "A8b" i + inputNum "A8c" i

def cell_075_a10_total_interest (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  cell_074_a8e_home_mortgage_interest i + inputNum "A9" i

def cell_076_a14_total_gifts_to_charity (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  inputNum "A11" i + inputNum "A12" i + inputNum "A13" i

def cell_077_a17_total_itemized_deductions (i : Inputs) : Float :=
  cell_070_a4_medical_deduction i +
  cell_073_a7_total_taxes i +
  cell_075_a10_total_interest i +
  cell_076_a14_total_gifts_to_charity i +
  inputNum "A15" i +
  inputNum "A16" i

end F1040sa

```

We show an example formalization of a portion of IRS Schedule A (Itemized Deductions) as executable symbolic functions in Lean. Each tax-form line is represented as a deterministic function whose inputs correspond to taxpayer-provided values or outputs of previously computed lines. The example includes the implementation of the post-OBBA 2025 State and Local Tax (SALT) deduction cap, which encodes statutory thresholds, phase-outs, and minimum floors directly in executable logic. The resulting computation graph preserves the structure of the tax form while enabling formal verification, automated testing, and neuro-symbolic correspondence between natural-language tax instructions and machine-executable legal rules.

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